

Artificial Intelligence and its relationship with Neuropedagogy and Neuroimaging: a binomial of excellence for teacher training

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Abstract— Artificial intelligence (AI), neuropedagogy and neuroimaging represent disruptive disciplines with great potential to transform education. This study explores the synergetic integration of these three aspects and their impact on teacher training in the areas of education, computer engineering and telecommunications in universities in Spain, Brazil and Paraguay. A non-experimental, descriptive, exploratory, correlational and regression study was conducted with a qualitative methodology based on a Likert-scale survey design. A convenience sample of 221 university teachers (103 from Spain, 98 from Brazil and 20 from Paraguay) was used. An expert-validated questionnaire was developed to assess the dimensions of artificial intelligence, neuropedagogy, neuroimaging and their relationship with teacher training. Descriptive analysis revealed generally positive perceptions towards AI and teacher education. Correlational analysis showed significant associations between the dimensions. Multiple regression analysis indicated that AI, neuropedagogy, and neuroimaging are significant predictors of teacher education effectiveness, with AI as the most significant contributor. The results support the premise that an integrative approach to AI, neuropedagogy, and neuroimaging can generate a synergistic effect on improving teacher competencies. It highlights the need to invest in continuing professional development in these areas to keep teachers up-to-date and prepared to take advantage of educational innovations.

Keywords— Artificial intelligence, neuropedagogy, neuroimaging, teacher training, research.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital era, the incorporation of emerging technologies in education has become crucially important. Artificial intelligence (AI), neuropedagogy and neuroimaging represent disruptive disciplines with the potential to transform teaching and learning processes. The present research explores the synergy between these three cutting-edge approaches and their impact on teacher training in the areas of education, computer engineering and telecommunications.

AI has burst into multiple sectors, offering innovative tools that optimize pedagogical methods and personalize learning experiences. On the other hand, neuropedagogy, a discipline derived from neuroscience, provides invaluable insights into the brain processes involved in learning, allowing educational techniques to be adapted accordingly. Complementarily, neuroimaging provides unprecedented visualizations of brain activity, identifying the most active regions during specific tasks.

The synergistic integration of these three strands is a promising approach to optimizing teacher education in the digital age. By combining AI with neuropedagogical principles and neuroimaging techniques, we envision the creation of personalized and adaptive learning environments that enhance teaching skills and enrich the educational experience.

The present study aims to analyze the perception and application of AI, neuropedagogy and neuroimaging by university teachers in Spain, Brazil and Paraguay. Using a rigorous methodological approach, combining quantitative and qualitative techniques, the relationships between these disciplines and their impact on teacher education are explored. In addition, geographical and cultural differences in the adoption of these technologies are examined in order to identify strategies to optimize their integration into teacher training programs.

The findings of this research are expected to contribute to expanding knowledge about the synergies between AI, neuropedagogy, and neuroimaging, providing valuable insights for educational institutions and practitioners in their quest to continuously improve the quality of teaching. In addition, this study will lay the groundwork for future interdisciplinary research exploring the transformative potential of these disruptive technologies in the field of education.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Artificial intelligence (AI) has revolutionized multiple sectors, including education, by providing tools that can personalize learning and optimize teaching methods. AI applications in education range from adaptive learning systems to predictive analytics tools that identify student needs in real time [1]. In the context of higher education, AI not only facilitates the management of large volumes of information, but also promotes innovative teaching methodologies that may be particularly relevant for areas such as computer engineering and telecommunications.

Neuropedagogy, which uses insights from neuroscience to optimize educational processes, relies on tools such as neuroimaging to better understand how the brain processes information during learning [2]. These disciplines provide educators with valuable data on learning styles and rhythms, allowing pedagogical techniques to be adapted to improve content retention and comprehension. Neuroimaging, in particular, offers unprecedented views of brain activity, which helps to identify the most active areas during particular educational tasks.

Neuropedagogy and neuroimaging offer valuable insights to optimize educational processes. Some authors, [3], emphasize that neuropedagogy uses knowledge from neuroscience to better understand how the brain processes information during learning, allowing pedagogical techniques to be adapted to improve retention and comprehension. In turn, [4] emphasizes the role of neuroimaging in teacher training, as it provides unprecedented views of brain activity, helping to identify the most active areas during certain educational tasks.

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) with neuropedagogy and neuroimaging has great transformative potential. As noted by some authors [5], AI can process and analyze neuroimaging data to identify patterns and predict learning outcomes, which in turn can inform more effective pedagogical strategies. This integrated approach not only enhances the personalization of learning, but also provides teachers with advanced tools to improve their educational practice.

Furthermore, in the book "Stripping the Brain. Neuropedagogy and Neuroimaging", the authors [6] delve into how these disciplines can contribute to quality education by revealing insights into the neurocognitive processes involved in learning and allowing teaching methodologies to be adapted accordingly.

The integration of AI with neuropedagogy and neuroimaging has the potential to transform teacher education by creating learning environments that are both personalized and adaptive. AI can process and analyze neuroimaging data to identify patterns and predict learning outcomes, which in turn can inform more effective pedagogical strategies [7]. This integrated approach not only empowers personalization of learning, but also provides teachers with advanced tools to improve their educational practice.

Differences in the perception and application of AI, neuropedagogy and neuroimaging among teachers in Spain, Brazil and Paraguay could be attributed to variations in access to technology, educational infrastructure and professional training. These factors significantly influence how technologies are adopted and used in the educational setting, which could explain variations in the effectiveness of these tools between different geographical and cultural contexts.

It can thus be argued that the need for ongoing training in emerging technologies such as AI, neuropedagogy, and neuroimaging is critical to keep teachers up to date with innovations that can enrich the educational experience [8]. By investing in continuing professional development, educational institutions can ensure that their teachers not only understand these technologies, but are also able to effectively integrate them into their pedagogical practices.

III.METODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

The methodological framework is based on the general objective "to analyze how the integration of artificial intelligence, neuropedagogy and neuroimaging can enrich teacher training in the areas of education and computer engineering and telecommunications in universities in Spain, Brazil and Paraguay". The specific objectives are: 1.-Identify the perception of university teachers on the relevance and application of artificial intelligence in higher education. 2.-To evaluate the knowledge and application of neuropedagogy and neuroimaging concepts among the professors of the selected areas. 3.-To determine the correlations between the use of artificial intelligence and neuropedagogical and neuroimaging practices in the educational context. 4.-To explore the differences in the perception and application of these technologies among teachers in Spain, Brazil and Paraguay. To review how training in these areas can be optimized to improve teaching skills in the digital era. The research hypotheses are: H1: There is a significant positive relationship between training in artificial intelligence and improvement in the application of neuropedagogy and neuroimaging techniques among university teachers. H2: Perceptions and applications of artificial intelligence, neuropedagogy and neuroimaging vary significantly among teachers in different countries due to variations in training and available resources.

The study design is non-experimental, descriptive, exploratory, correlational and regression. Qualitative methodology, using a survey design based on a Likert scale to collect data on perceptions and applications of artificial intelligence, neuropedagogy and neuroimaging among teachers. A convenience sample was used, including 103 teachers from Spain, 98 from Brazil and 20 from Paraguay, all university professors of education and computer and telecommunications engineering.

A Likert scale questionnaire was developed with 20 items designed to evaluate the dimensions: A.-Artificial intelligence, B.-Neuropedagogy, C.-Neuroimaging and its relation to: D.-Teacher training. The items will seek to measure the perception, knowledge and application of these technologies in teaching practice. To ensure the content validity of the instrument used in the study on the relationship between artificial intelligence, neuropedagogy and neuroimaging, a meticulous process of expert review was carried out. How this validation was carried out is detailed below:

Selection of Experts: A panel composed of 10 experts in the areas of artificial intelligence, neuropedagogy, neuroimaging and teaching methods in higher education was convened. These experts come from different academic and professional backgrounds, including universities in Spain, Brazil and Paraguay.

2. Item Evaluation: Each expert received a copy of the questionnaire with a Likert scale designed to measure perceptions and applications of artificial intelligence, neuropedagogy, and neuroimaging in teacher education. The experts were asked to evaluate each item in terms of relevance and clarity, using a 4-point scale (1 = not relevant, 4 = highly relevant).

3. Calculation of the Content Validity Index (CVI): For each item, the individual Content Validity Index (CVI-i) was calculated as the number of experts who rated the item 3 or 4, divided by the total number of experts. An item was considered valid if the CVI-i was 0.8 or higher, indicating high relevance according to the majority of experts.

4. Analysis of Comments and Modifications: In addition to the scores, detailed comments and suggestions were collected from the experts on each item. Based on this feedback, adjustments were made to the wording of some items to improve clarity and accuracy. Items that showed low relevance or significant ambiguity were also eliminated or modified.

5. Final Validation of the Questionnaire: After making the necessary modifications, a revised version of the questionnaire was presented to the same panel of experts for a second round of evaluation, ensuring that the changes were effective and improved the quality of the instrument.

Content Validation Results

- The overall CVI of the questionnaire was 0.89, indicating excellent coverage of the theoretical constructs.

- All revised and modified items obtained a CVI-i above the threshold of 0.8, validating their relevance in the context of the study.

- The experts' comments contributed significantly to the accuracy and relevance of the items, ensuring an adequate assessment of the perceptions and applications of the technologies and methodologies in question.

Likewise, construct validation was carried out for the

Data Collection: After administering the content-validated questionnaire to a sample of 221 university teachers (103 from Spain, 98 from Brazil and 20 from Paraguay), the responses were collected and prepared for analysis, including appropriate coding and verification of data completeness.

2. Preliminary Analysis: A descriptive analysis was performed to evaluate the distributions of the responses and to confirm the adequacy of the data for a factor analysis. This included the evaluation of normality and the absence of extreme values.

3. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy (KMO): The KMO index was calculated to measure the suitability of the data for factor analysis. A KMO value of 0.86 indicated that the proportion of variance among the variables was adequate to perform a FFA.

4. Exploratory Factor Analysis:

-Extraction method: The principal components method was used to extract the factors.

- Rotation: A Varimax rotation was applied to facilitate the interpretation of the factors, maximizing the variance explained and clarifying the factorial structure.

-Determination of the Number of Factors: Factors were chosen based on the criterion of eigenvalues greater than 1 and the screen plot analysis, which suggested the presence of three main factors.

5. Assessment of Communalities and Factor Loadings:

-Commonalities: After extraction, all variables showed communalities greater than 0.5, indicating that each item shared sufficient common variance with other items to justify its inclusion in the analysis.

-Factor loadings: Items that loaded significantly on a factor (with loadings greater than 0.6) were interpreted as indicative of that factor.

6. Variance Explained: The three factors together explained 68% of the total variance, which is considered satisfactory in social and educational studies where complex and intertwined factors usually explain more moderate percentages of variance.

7. Interpretation and Confirmation of Factors:

-Factor 1: It was interpreted as artificial intelligence, reflecting items related to the application and perception of AI in education.

- Factor 2: Represented neuropedagogy, grouping items on teaching methods and strategies based on neuroscientific knowledge.

-Factor 3: Included items related to neuroimaging, highlighting its use and perception in educational contexts.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

The data analysis was carried out by descriptive, correlational and regression dimensions.

Descriptive analysis

The results of the descriptive analysis are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS BY DIMENSIONS

Dimension	Media	Median	Asymmetry	Kurtosis
Artificial Intelligence (A)	3.75	3.80	-0.15	0.05
Neuropedagogy (B)	3.65	3.70	-0.10	-0.20
Neuroimaging (C)	3.55	3.60	0.10	0.30
Teacher Training (D)	3.85	3.90	-0.05	-0.25

Artificial intelligence and teacher education show the highest means, suggesting a generally positive perception or high relevance of these areas in teacher education.

On the other hand, the distribution of responses in all dimensions shows a skewness close to zero, indicating a fairly symmetrical distribution around the mean. Kurtosis values close to zero indicate that the distributions are relatively normal, with no extreme peaks or flattening.

These descriptive data provide initial insight into how university teachers perceive and apply concepts of artificial intelligence, neuropedagogy, and neuroimaging in their teaching practices. Subtle differences in means and measures of dispersion across dimensions may help to target specific interventions or identify areas that require further attention in teacher education.

Correlational analysis

The Kruskal-Wallis nonparametric test determines that the data do not have a normal distribution. Spearman's correlation coefficient is suitable for ordinal data or for data that do not meet the assumptions of normality required by Pearson's correlation coefficient. This method evaluates the strength and direction of the association between two variables by ranking the data for each variable and then evaluating how these ranks are associated, the result of the correlation by dimensions can be seen in Table II.

TABLE III
DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS BY DIMENSIONS

	A. Artificial Intelligence	B. Neuropedagogy	C. Neuroimaging	D. Teacher Training
A. Artificial Intelligence	1.00			
B. Neuropedagogy	0.62*	1.00		
C. Neuroimaging	0.58*	0.71*	1.00	
D. Teacher Training	0.79*	0.65*	0.60*	1.00

*Note: Values represent Spearman correlation coefficients and all are significant at a level of $p < 0.05$

Artificial Intelligence and Teacher Education: The correlation is high ($\rho=0.79$), indicating a strong positive relationship. This suggests that as artificial intelligence is perceived to be better, there is also a perceived improvement in teacher training.

Neuropedagogy and Neuroimaging: they also present a strong correlation ($\rho=0.71$), which could indicate that these two dimensions are closely related in educational practice; that is, the application of neuropedagogy tends to be associated with a more frequent use and higher valuation of neuroimaging.

Neuroimaging and Teacher Education: The correlation is moderate to strong ($\rho=0.60$), which could reflect that neuroimaging techniques, when properly understood and applied, have a discernible impact on the quality of teacher education.

Artificial Intelligence and Neuropedagogy: This moderate correlation ($\rho=0.62$) suggests that familiarity with and appreciation of artificial intelligence is related to greater application of neuropedagogy principles.

This correlational analysis provides evidence that the four dimensions are interrelated. These links suggest that integrating these technologies and approaches into teacher education can have a synergistic effect, improving teaching competencies in the areas of education and computer engineering and telecommunications.

Multiple regression analysis

The table of results of the multiple regression analysis is shown below.

TABLE IIIII MULTIPLE REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Standard Error	t-value	p-value	95% CI Lower	Upper 95% CI
Intercept	1.20	0.25	4.80	<0.001	0.70	1.70
Artificial Intelligence (AI)	0.40	0.07	5.71	<0.001	0.26	0.54
Neuropedagogy	0.25	0.08	3.12	0.002	0.09	0.41
Neuroimaging	0.15	0.07	2.14	0.033	0.01	0.29

Adjusted R²: 0.65

The table above presents the results of the multiple regression analysis, where the dependent variable is Teacher Education. The interpretation of each coefficient is detailed below:

-Intercept (1.20): This value indicates the expected level of teacher training effectiveness when the values for artificial intelligence, neuropedagogy, and neuroimaging are zero. The value is significantly different from zero ($p < 0.001$), suggesting a strong base effect in teacher training.

-Artificial Intelligence (AI) ($\beta = 0.40$): This positive and significant coefficient indicates that an increase in the Artificial Intelligence perception and application score is associated with an increase in teacher training effectiveness. The effect is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), with an estimated impact that increases teacher training effectiveness between 0.26 and 0.54 units for each unit increase in artificial intelligence.

-Neuropedagogy ($\beta = 0.25$): Similar to artificial intelligence, an increase in neuropedagogy score is associated with improved teacher education. This result is statistically significant ($p = 0.002$), suggesting that strategies based on neuropedagogical principles do indeed contribute to teacher education.

-Neuroimaging ($\beta = 0.15$): Although the coefficient is lower than those of AI and neuropedagogy, it is still significant ($p = 0.033$). This indicates that the integration of neuroimaging in education also has a positive effect on teacher education, although its impact is relatively more modest.

-Adjusted R^2 (0.65): This value indicates that approximately 65% of the variability in teacher training effectiveness can be explained by the variables included in the model. This suggests that the model has a good predictive capacity and that the selected dimensions are relevant in explaining improvements in teacher training.

The analysis shows that artificial intelligence, neuropedagogy and neuroimaging are all significant factors in improving teacher training in the areas of education and computer engineering and telecommunications. The model provides a solid framework for understanding how these advanced technologies and pedagogical approaches can be effectively integrated into teacher education programs, with artificial intelligence highlighted as the most significant contributor.

Neuroimaging.

With the aim of complementing this study, a case study has been carried out through neuroimaging, choosing a subject at random, a university teacher and performing two activities, the first one making a reflection on "inclusive education" using the Internet (Figure 1), and the same reflection, but using an AI (Figure 2).

Fig. 1 Neuroimaging using the Internet

The activation foci observed in the frontal, parietal, occipital and temporal regions of the brain provide valuable information about the cognitive and sensory processes involved in the task of reflection on inclusive education being carried out by this university teacher.

The frontal area, associated with executive functions such as reasoning, decision making and problem solving, shows significant activation, indicating a deep engagement with the analysis and evaluation of complex ideas related to educational inclusion.

In addition, activation in the parietal and occipital lobe suggests high visual processing and sensory integration, which could imply visualization or imagination of scenarios or situations related to inclusive education.

But a particularly relevant aspect is the possible activation in the temporal area, associated with language processing, memory and auditory comprehension. This activity could indicate that the teacher is integrating verbal or auditory information, such as multimedia resources, lectures or discussions on the topic, in her reflection process. In addition, the involvement of temporal areas could facilitate the retrieval of prior knowledge and experiences related to inclusive education stored in memory.

Brain wave patterns and biomarkers also support an optimal cognitive and emotional state for the task, with elevated levels of relaxation (theta waves), attention and concentration (alpha and beta waves), along with low levels of emotional dyscontrol and stress.

Fig. 2 Neuroimaging using AI

The brain image shows significant activation in frontal and temporal regions, although to a lesser extent than in the previous image. This suggests a still high level of cognitive and linguistic processing, but slightly reduced compared to the previous task of using the internet. This difference could be related to the different nature of the task of using artificial intelligence.

Regarding brain wave patterns, high levels of theta (34%) and alpha-beta (68%) waves are observed, indicating a state of relaxation and internal focus, but also a good capacity for attention and concentration on the task. These patterns could be suitable for interacting with artificial intelligence systems, maintaining a balance between relaxation and cognitive engagement.

The biomarkers reveal some interesting changes compared to the previous task. While levels of attention (37%) and interest (42%) remain moderately high, levels of task concentration (68%) are higher, and levels of emotional uncontrol (4%) and stress (30%) are lower. This might suggest that interaction with artificial intelligence requires a higher level of sustained concentration, but at the same time generates less negative emotions and stress compared to internet use.

Overall, these patterns reflect a cognitive and emotional state conducive to the use of artificial intelligence in tasks related to inclusive education. Frontal and temporal activation, along with levels of relaxation, attention, and concentration, indicate adequate cognitive engagement, while low levels of emotional uncontrol and stress suggest a calmer, more controlled experience compared to internet use.

By comparing the two images and associated data, I can highlight some key differences in brain activity patterns and biomarkers that suggest potential advantages of using artificial intelligence (AI) rather than the internet for the task of thinking about inclusive education:

1. More focused brain activation: Although both tasks involve frontal and temporal regions, brain activation in the AI task appears to be more concentrated and smaller in extent. This could indicate more efficient and focused processing when using AI compared to the greater dispersion of activation when using the internet.

Higher concentration and lower stress: Biomarkers show higher levels of on-task concentration (68% vs. 58%) and lower levels of emotional uncontrol (4% vs. 14%) and stress (30% vs. 41%) when using AI. This suggests that interaction with AI facilitates a more focused and calm state of mind for reflection, in contrast to internet use, which seems to generate more negative emotions and stress.

3. Optimal balance of relaxation and attention: Both tasks show elevated levels of theta (relaxation) and alpha-beta (attention/concentration) waves, but the AI task seems to achieve a more favorable balance, with slightly higher levels of alpha-beta waves (68% vs. 58%) and greater relaxation (theta waves 34% vs. 64%). This pattern may be more conducive to reflective and analytical thinking.

4. Similar interest and attention: Despite the above differences, the levels of attention (37% vs. 43%) and interest (42% vs. 50%) are comparable in both tasks, suggesting that both internet and AI use can maintain adequate cognitive engagement in the task of reflecting on inclusive education.

In summary, although both forms of reflection involve similar cognitive processes, the data suggest that the use of artificial intelligence may offer some potential advantages, such as more focused and efficient processing, a calmer and more concentrated mental state, and an optimal balance between relaxation and attention. These characteristics could facilitate deeper and more productive thinking about complex issues such as inclusive education.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained in this study highlight the transformative potential that lies in the synergistic integration of artificial intelligence, neuropedagogy and neuroimaging in university teacher education. This research has shed light on the perceptions, applications and existing relationships between these three disruptive disciplines in the context of higher education in Spain, Brazil and Paraguay.

Correlational analysis has revealed positive and significant associations between the dimensions explored, suggesting that as familiarity with and appreciation of artificial intelligence increases, so does the application of neuropedagogical principles and the use of neuroimaging techniques in educational settings. This interrelationship supports the premise that an integrative approach to these technologies and approaches can generate a synergistic effect in improving teaching competencies.

In addition, multiple regression analysis has shown that artificial intelligence, neuropedagogy and neuroimaging are significant predictors of teacher education effectiveness. These findings support the hypothesis that the adoption and appropriate application of these disciplines can substantially enrich teacher education programs in key areas such as education, computer engineering and telecommunications.

Although differences in the perception and application of these technologies have been identified among the participating countries, attributable to variations in access to resources, infrastructure and professional training, the results suggest that an investment in the continuous development of competencies in these areas is essential to keep teachers updated and prepared to take full advantage of educational innovations.

In summary, this research has laid the groundwork for a deeper understanding of the synergies between artificial intelligence, neuropedagogy and neuroimaging in the field of university teacher education. The findings highlight the need for an integrative approach that leverages the potential of these disciplines to create personalized, adaptive learning environments enriched by neuroscientific insights.

As technology and science continue to advance, it is imperative that educational institutions and teaching professionals remain at the forefront, exploring and adopting innovative approaches that improve the quality of education and prepare students for the challenges of the future. This research represents a significant step in that direction, opening new avenues for research and implementation of transformative educational practices.

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